

Full title: **Clean clinker production via calcium looping process**

Acronym: **CLEANKER**

Type of action: **H2020-LCE-2016-2017/LCE-29-2017**

Grant Agreement number: **764816**

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Project Management Handbook describing all commonly-agreed internal project management procedures

WP1 – Deliverable D1.2

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PU=Public

CO=Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

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Short description
Reference for the consortium by describing all commonly-agreed internal project management procedures, including financial administration, procedures for dissemination and submission of scientific papers and abstracts to journals and conferences.

The opinions expressed in this document reflect only the author's view and in no way reflect the European Commission's opinions. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

History of changes

Version	DATE	Changes	Author
V0.1	2018-01-08	First release to be reviewed by all partners	Martina Fantini (LEAP)
V0.2	2018-11-30	Second release. Changes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tables 1.2, 1.3, 1.4, 3.2; • Figures 3.2, 3.3, 3.4; • 5.3.1 Deliverables. Due to Amendment request and change in USTUTT team	Martina Fantini (LEAP)

Abstract

This deliverable gives a quick overview of the most relevant managerial aspects of the project, outlining rules and responsibilities of partners aimed at ensuring a good quality and progress of the work.

This document summarises all the required knowledge for the good management of the documentation of the project and contains all information related to the management strategy, structure of the consortium, working procedures, reporting issues, templates to be used, etc. This guide acts as a reference source for all Consortium members, covering day-to-day activities including the clarification of legal and financial aspects of the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement that may need further explanations to beneficiaries.

The first version of this document is delivered on December 2017 (M3) but it can be modified during the life of the project. This document will be updated and extended, if needed, through the life of CLEANKER project, including relevant issues and changes in the project or procedures. Every time the document is updated, a new version of the report will be sent to all the partners that will be duly informed about the updates and the changes made with respect to the previous version.

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this Handbook is overruled by the Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement.

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1. CLEANKER STRUCTURE AND BASIS

1.1 Participants

The beneficiaries of CLEANKER are listed in the Grant Agreement, in the Consortium Agreement and presented in Table 1-1.

Table 1-1: List of Beneficiaries

Participant No.	Participant organization name	Partner short name	Country
1 (CO)	LABORATORIO ENERGIA AMBIENTE PIACENZA	LEAP	ITALY
2	BUZZI UNICEM SPA	BUZZI	ITALY
3	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	SPAIN
4	ITALCEMENTI FABBRICHE RIUNITE CEMENTO SPA	ITC-HCG	ITALY
5	IKN GMBH INGENIEURBURO-KUHLERBAU-NEUSTADT	IKN	GERMANY
6	LAPPEENRANNAN TEKNILLINEN YLIOPISTO	LUT	FINLAND
7	POLITECNICO DI MILANO	POLIMI	ITALY
8	QUANTIS	QUANTIS	SWITZERLAND
9	TALLINNA TEHNIKAULIKOOL	TUT	ESTONIA
10	TSINGHUA UNIVERSITY	TSIU	CHINA
11	UNIVERSITAET STUTTGART	USTUTT	GERMANY
12	VDZ gGmbH	VDZ	GERMANY
13	AMICI DELLA TERRA ONLUS	AdT	ITALY

Beneficiary number 12, VDZ, has its subsidiary, Forschungsinstitut der Zementindustrie GmbH (FIZ GmbH), as Linked Third Party. VDZ remains responsible towards the Commission/Agency for the work carried out by FIZ. Moreover, the beneficiaries are financially responsible for any undue amount paid by the Commission/Agency as reimbursement of costs for their linked third parties¹.

New contacts, changes and / or corrections to the list of contacts should be addressed to LEAP in order to keep updated the contact details of beneficiaries involved

¹ Annotated Model Grant Agreement V4.0, page 149

1.2 Contracts

1.2.1 Grant Agreement

The Grant Agreement is the master reference when in doubt. CLEANKER Grant Agreement number is 764816 and it is composed of:

- Terms and conditions;
- Annex 1: Description of the action;
 - Part A: it contains the cover page, the project summary, the list of participants and the work plan tables, which provide details on the implementation of the action;
 - Part B: it is the narrative part of the description of the action.
- Annex 2: Estimated budget for the action;
- Annex 3: Accession forms;
- Annex 4: Model for the financial statements;
- Annex 5: Model for the certificate on the financial statements (CFS);
- Annex 6: Model for the certificate on methodology.

The Grant Agreement and its annexes are available in “Participant Portal > My Project > CLEANKER MP > Process Documents > Grant Agreement” and in “www.cleanker.eu > Contracts > Grant Agreement”.

At the time being, no amendments to the Grant Agreement have been requested.

1.2.2 Consortium Agreement

The Consortium Agreement, the private agreement between the beneficiaries that sets out the rights and obligations among the participants, complements the Grant Agreement and does not contain any provision contrary to it.

The signed Version 1 of CLEANKER Consortium Agreement was sent to the partners on June 26th, 2017.

However, during the Kick-off Meeting (KoM), the General Assembly agreed on:

- Broke down the pre-payment in two instalments in order to reduce the risks ensuing from the contingent default of a Party (Clause 7.3.2);
- Give to the Executive Board full responsibility of deliverables approval before submission to EC by the Coordinator (Clause 6.3.2.3.6).

Consequently, two Amendments to the Version 1 of the Consortium Agreement were done and the signed Version 1.1 of the Consortium Agreement was sent to the partners on November 30th, 2017.

The Consortium Agreement is available in “www.cleanker.eu > Contracts > Consortium Agreement”.

1.3 Project duration

The effective start of the project is 01/10/2017. It ends 48 months later, on 30/09/2021.

1.4 Budget

The estimated budget for the action is set out in Annex II to the Grant Agreement and the Maximum grant amount to the project is 8,972,201.25 € (GA, Article 5).

The Annex 1, Part B, includes a section “resources to be committed” where the use of resources planned for the implementation of the project are described.

1.5 CLEANKER management structure

As outlined and detailed in D1.1, “Project Management Plan”, the organizational structure and decision-making mechanism of the project are shown diagrammatically in Figure 1-1. Members of each body except for the Advisory Board and the Public Awareness Board that will be nominated within six months from the start of the project, can be found in Table 1-2, Table 1-3 and Table 1-4. For any detail regarding roles, responsibilities, meeting scheduling etc., refer to D1.1.

Figure 1-1: CLEANKER project management structure

Table 1-2: CLEANKER GA representatives and deputies

	Partner short name	GA member	GA deputy
1	LEAP	Stefano Consonni (chairman)	Martina Fantini
2	BUZZI	Fulvio Canonico	Mario Balocco
3	CSIC	Carlos Abanades	Borja Arias
4	ITC-HCG	Giovanni Cinti	
5	IKN	Jörg Hammerich	Reinhard Köhler
6	LUT	Timo Hyppänen	Kari Myöhänen
7	POLIMI	Matteo Romano	Stefano Campanari
8	QUANTIS	Sessa Filippo	Anna Kounina
9	TUT	Alla Shogenova	Mai Uibu
10	TSIU	Li Zhenshan	
11	USTUTT	Max Schmid	Matthias Hornberger
12	VDZ	Volker Hoenig	Kristina Fleiger
13	AdT	Monica Tommasi	Donovan Baldassarri

Table 1-3: CLEANKER EB and IMB members

Partner #	Partner short name	EB member	IMB member
1	LEAP	Martina Fantini	Alberto Sogni
2	BUZZI	Mario Balocco	Luigi Buzzi
3	CSIC	Borja Arias	Borja Arias
4	ITC-HCG	Giovanni Cinti	Giovanni Cinti
5	IKN	Jörg Hammerich	Reinhard Köhler
6	LUT	Kari Myöhänen	Kari Myöhänen
7	POLIMI	Matteo Romano	Stefano Campanari, Matteo Romano
8	QUANTIS	Sessa Filippo	Sessa Filippo
9	TUT	Alla Shogenova	Alla Shogenova
10	TSIU	Li Zhenshan	Li Zhenshan
11	USTUTT	Max Schmid	Max Schmid
12	VDZ	Volker Hoenig	Volker Hoenig
13	AdT	Donovan Baldassarri	Raffaele Scialdoni

Table 1-4: CLEANKER WP leaders

WP	WP Title	WP leader	LEADER
1	Project management and coordination	LEAP	Martina Fantini
2	Engineering and construction of the CaL demonstration system at TRL7	IKN	Jörg Hammerich
3	Operation and testing of the CaL demonstration system in an operating, commercial cement plant	BUZZI	Mario Balocco
4	Comparative characterization of raw meals for CaL	USTUTT	Max Schmid
5	Process modelling and integration	POLIMI	Matteo Romano
6	Technology scale-up, economic analysis and LCA	VDZ	Kristina Fleiger
7	Transport, utilization and storage study	TUT	Alla Shogenova
8	Exploitation	ITC-HCG	Giovanni Cinti
9	Dissemination, communication and knowledge sharing	LEAP	Martina Fantini

1.6 Contacts

For effective communication between beneficiaries, different mailing lists have been created:

- “CLEANKER”: all members of the consortium;
- “CLEANKER COMPLETE”: all members of the consortium plus Public Awareness Board and Advisory Board members;
- “CLEANKER GA”: official members and deputies of the General Assembly plus the Coordinator;
- “CLEANKER EB”: members of the Executive Board plus the Coordinator;
- “CLEANKER IMB”: members of the Innovation Management Board plus the Coordinator;
- “CLEANKER WP leaders”: WP leaders plus the Coordinator;
- “CLEANKER WP-WPnumber-”: WP-WPnumber- persons involved plus the Coordinator.

The creation of new mailing lists or any change to an existing one, will be managed by the Coordinator (email: martina.fantini@polimi.it).

2. PARTICIPANT PORTAL ROLES

The Participant Portal is the entry point for electronic administration of EU-funded research and innovation projects, and hosts the services for managing proposals and projects throughout their lifecycle.

2.1 Main roles and access rights

In managing EU projects, “organization” and “project” roles have to be distinguished. Organization roles are linked to the whole entity and its data (without any access to the project). Project roles are defined project by project and cover all possible cases for allowing access to a project’s data (read/write/submit).

2.1.1 Organization roles

- Legal Entity Appointed Representative (LEAR) serves as a trusted administrative contact for the Commission, providing reliable information at the level of the organization. There can be only one LEAR per organization.
- Account Administrator (AccAd). LEAR may delegate tasks to one or more Account Administrators.
- The Financial Statement Authorised Signatory (FSIGN) is the person authorised to sign Forms C for their organisation. The FSIGN is nominated by the LEAR or an Account Administrator under the "My Organisations" tab > "RO" icon (consequently the nomination of LEARs is now mandatory). An unlimited number of FSIGNs can be nominated for an organisation. Then it's up to the Primary Coordinator Contacts, the Coordinator Contacts and Participant Contacts to assign FSIGNs to specific projects, becoming at this moment Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGNs).
- The Legal Statement Authorised Signatory (LSIGN): to appoint LSIGNs, the procedure is the same as for FSIGNs. The LSIGN has to be nominated by someone having an organisation role (LEAR, Account Administrators). The LSIGN must then be appointed to one or several project(s) by someone having a project role (Primary Coordinator Contact, Coordinator Contacts or Participant Contacts) in said project(s). An organization can have one or more LSIGNs per project.

2.1.2 Project roles

- The Primary Coordinator Contact (PCoCo) of a project is a unique role, set/modified by the Commission/Agency. All Primary Coordinator Contacts have full, read/write access to their own and the consortium's common e-forms, and can submit to the Commission/Agency via the Participant Portal.
- Coordinator Contacts (CoCo) can be nominated by the Primary Coordinator Contact. All Coordinator Contacts have full, read/write access to their own and the common eforms, and can submit to the Commission/Agency via the Participant Portal.
- Participant Contacts (PaCo) can be nominated either by the Primary Coordinator Contact or by Participant Contacts. All Participant Contacts can submit e-forms to the Coordinator Contacts via the Participant Portal. They have read/write access to their own forms and read-only rights to certain common forms.

- Task Managers (TaMa) can read, modify and save their own entity's forms.
- Team Members (TeMe) have read-only rights to the entity's own forms.
- The Project Financial Statement Authorised Signatory (PFSIGN) is the person authorised to sign CLEANKER Forms C for its organisation. This role is assigned by the Primary Coordinator Contacts, the Coordinator Contacts and Participant Contacts.
- The Project Legal Statement Authorised Signatory (PLSIGN) is be nominated by Primary Coordinator Contact, Coordinator Contacts or Participant Contacts and has the right to sign grant agreement and amendments on behalf of the organization.

A summary of the rights associated with roles is shown in Figure 2-1.

Figure 2-1: Which roles can perform which action?

2.2 How to add or revoke roles in the participant portal

Except for the Primary Coordinator Contact (PCoCo) and the LEAR, every role must be modified by the Participants.

Each user can be nominated or revoked by another user, as follows:

- The Primary Coordinator Contact can nominate/revoke Coordinator Contacts, Task Managers and Team Members of the coordinating entity, Participant Contacts of other participating organisations, and assign LSIGNs and FSIGNs to a project.
- Coordinator Contacts can nominate/revoke other Coordinator Contacts, Task Managers and Team Members of the coordinating entity, and assign LSIGNs and FSIGNs to a project.
- Participant Contacts can nominate/revoke other Participant Contacts, Task Managers and Team Members of their own entity, and assign LSIGNs and FSIGNs to a project.

- The Legal Entity Appointed Representative (LEAR) can nominate Account Administrators, LSIGNs and FSIGNs for his/her own entity.
- Account Administrators can nominate LSIGNs and FSIGNs for his/her own entity.

2.3 Roles in CLEANKER

Roles appointed by each beneficiary can be checked via the Participant Portal under “My Projects” choosing the option “PC: Project Consortium”.

3. PROJECT STRUCTURE - EXECUTION OF WORK

The CLEANKER project consists of nine work packages (WPs) interacting as follows (Figure 3-1).

Figure 3-1: CLEANKER WPs structure

The main characteristics in terms of human effort and timing are the following:

Table 3-1: Characteristics of the WPs

WP No	WP Title	WP leader	Person-Months	Start month	End month
WP1	Project management and coordination	LEAP	28,0	1	48
WP2	Engineering and construction of the CaL demonstration system at TRL7	IKN	87,0	1	24
WP3	Operation and testing of the CaL demonstration system in an operating, commercial cement plant	BUZZI	115,0	21	46
WP4	Comparative characterization of raw meals for CaL	USTUTT	87,0	1	38
WP5	Process modelling and integration	POLIMI	118,0	1	46
WP6	Technology scale-up, economic analysis and LCA	VDZ	48,0	7	45
WP7	Transport, utilization and storage study	TUT	65,0	1	48
WP8	Exploitation	ITC-HCG	27,0	25	48
WP9	Dissemination, communication and knowledge sharing	LEAP	37,0	1	48

3.1.1 Work breakdown structure

The CLEANKER work breakdown structure on task level can be seen below (Figure 3-2) with Partner responsibilities on WP and Task level and names of WP leaders.

Figure 3-2: CLEANKER Work breakdown structure

3.1.2 Deliverables and Milestones

Monitoring the project implementation is a continuous task. Project deliverables (Article 19 of the GA) are the main outcome of CLEANKER project. The complete list can be found in Annex 1, part A of the CLEANKER Grant Agreement (Table 1.3.2) ordered by WP and in Table 3-2 in chronologically order.

Table 3-2: List of deliverables - cronological order

Deliv. no	Deliverable name	WP no.	Lead participant	Type	Dissemin. Level	Delivery date
D1.1	Detailed Project Management plan	1	LEAP	R	PU	M2
D4.1	Experimental test matrix for Vernasca raw meal characterization	4	POLIMI	R	CO	M2
D1.2	Project Management Handbook describing all commonly-agreed internal project management procedures	1	LEAP	R	PU	M3
D9.1	Development of a dissemination and communication plan of results.	9	LEAP	R	PU	M3
D2.3	Heat and mass balances of the demonstration plant under relevant operating conditions to support the design of the demonstration plant	2	POLIMI	R	CO	M6
D4.2	Experimental test matrix for characterization of other raw meals	4	POLIMI	R	CO	M6
D9.6	CLEANKER Newsletter (1)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M6
D9.14	CLEANKER website and social media account online	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M6
D2.1	Engineering and detailed design of the demonstration plant	2	IKN	R	CO	M9
D2.4	Definition of measuring points and instrumentation	2	VDZ	R	CO	M9
D4.3	Characterization of BUZZI demo-plant raw meal under	4	USTUTT	R	PU	M10

	realistic entrained flow conditions						
D7.3	Regional and national regulations, gaps and recommendations for CCUS scenarios	7	TUT	R	PU	M10	
D5.1	Kinetics rates for calcination and carbonation of Vernasca raw meal	5	CSIC	R	PU	M12	
D5.3	Report on first stage demo system simulations using the early phase simulations tool with non-validated physical submodels	5	POLIMI	R	CO	M12	
D9.2	First year technical report for ECRA	9	LEAP	R	CO	M12	
D9.7	CLEANKER Newsletter (2)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M12	
D7.1	Definition of a methodology for the development of a techno-economic study for CO ₂ transport, storage and utilization	7	TUT	R	PU	M14	
D2.2	Project execution plan including detailed equipment list and specifications	2	IKN	R	CO	M15	
D7.4	Lab-scale experiments on waste oils shale ash and CDW carbonation and recommendations for the design of the mineralization reactor in Vernasca	7	TUT	R	CO	M16	
D5.10	Configuration and preliminary performance of the CPU for two different CO ₂ target purities	5	LEAP	R	PU	M18	
D9.8	CLEANKER Newsletter (3)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M18	
D2.5	Safety and risk analysis for demonstration plant operations	2	BUZZI	R	PU	M21	
D5.8	Performance of CaL processes in full scale cement plants, with	5	POLIMI	R	CO	M21	

	full sensitivity analysis and comparison with benchmark					
D3.1	Experimental test matrix for first short trials	3	POLIMI	R	CO	M24
D4.6	Experimental determination of intrinsic calcination/carbonation kinetics for various raw meals	4	CSIC	R	CO	M24
D4.7	Experimental determination of macro-kinetic calcination/carbonation data for the investigated Chinese and reference raw meal qualities	4	TSIU	R	PU	M24
D5.5	Report on second stage demo system simulations	5	LUT	R	CO	M24
D6.4	Screening environmental LCA of the CLEANKER technology	6	QUANTIS	R	PU	M24
D7.5	Design and full specifications of the pilot facility for mineralization tests in Vernasca	7	BUZZI	DE M	PU	M24
D9.3	Second year technical report for ECRA	9	LEAP	R	CO	M24
D9.9	CLEANKER Newsletter (4)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M24
D3.3	Report on the first three short trials from the CaL demonstration plant	3	LEAP	R	PU	M30
D5.2	Screening of kinetic parameters and performance of several raw meals at particle level	5	CSIC	R	CO	M30
D5.4	Report on 1D and 3D model frames	5	LUT	R	CO	M30
D5.11	Final report on the optimal layout, performance and costs of the CPU for two different CO ₂ target purities, including also off-design evaluation	5	LEAP	R	PU	M30
D9.10	CLEANKER Newsletter (5)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M30
D6.2	Preliminary economic analysis of cement plants equipped with CaL process and comparison	6	VDZ	R	CO	M32

	with benchmark oxyfuel cement plant						
D3.4	Report on the fourth and fifth short trials from the CaL demonstration plant	3	LEAP	R	CO	M34	
D3.2	Experimental test matrix for long term tests	3	POLIMI	R	CO	M36	
D4.4	Comparative characterization of cement raw meal qualities for Calcium Looping	4	USTUTT	R	PU	M36	
D5.6	Tuning and validation of demo scale reactor models	5	LUT	R	CO	M36	
D7.2	Techno-economic modelling of selected local and regional CCUS scenarios for Vernasca, Kunda and Slantsy cement plants	7	TUT	R	PU	M36	
D9.4	Third year technical report for ECRA	9	LEAP	R	CO	M36	
D9.11	CLEANKER Newsletter (6)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M36	
D4.5	Guidelines on raw meal characterization for CaL applications	4	USTUTT	R	PU	M38	
D3.5	Report on the first two long run tests from the CaL demonstration plant	3	BUZZI	R	CO	M40	
D6.1	Scale-up study and capital cost estimation of full scale cement plant with CaL process	6	IKN	R	CO	M40	
D5.9	Final performance of the optimized CaL processes in full scale cement plants using validated reactor models	5	POLIMI	R	PU	M41	
D9.12	CLEANKER Newsletter (7)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M42	
D6.3	Full economic analysis of cement plants equipped with CaL, both newly designed and retrofitted, and final comparison with benchmark oxyfuel cement plant	6	VDZ	R	CO	M43	

D3.6	Report on the last two long run tests from the CaL demonstration plant, with calculation of demonstration plant key performance indexes	3	BUZZI	R	PU	M44
D7.6	Final report with results of the mineralization tests at Vernasca	7	BUZZI	R	CO	M44
D6.5	Final environmental LCA of the CLEANKER technology	6	QUANTIS	R	PU	M45
D8.1	Applicability of the CaL process in the ECRA oxyfuel demonstration project	8	VDZ	R	CO	M45
D3.7	Detailed report on operational data from short and long term tests	3	LEAP	R	CO	M46
D3.8	Report on best practice for using efficiently the CaL technology in Vernasca plant	3	BUZZI	R	CO	M46
D3.9	Detailed report on properties of calcined and recarbonated material collected from the CaL demonstrator during short and long term tests.	3	USTUTT	R	PU	M46
D5.7	Modelling of full scale units	5	LUT	R	CO	M46
D7.7	Results from casting concrete containing CaLooped CO ₂ trapped in the Vernasca demo system	7	BUZZI	R	CO	M48
D8.2	Business plans and economic analysis for commercial exploitation of CLEANKER technology in selected ITC-HCG and BUZZI plants	8	ITC-HCG	R	CO	M48
D8.3	Strategy report on exploitation of CLEANKER technology to market	8	LEAP	R	PU	M48
D9.5	Final technical report for ECRA	9	LEAP	R	CO	M48
D9.13	CLEANKER Newsletter (8)	9	LEAP	DEC	PU	M48
D9.15	User-friendly web-based footprinter.	9	QUANTIS	DEC	PU	M48

D9.16	CLEANKER Strategic conclusions	9	LEAP	R	PU	M48
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Each deliverable relates to one or more tasks of the project, thus, it has normally more contributors. There is a main responsible for each deliverable that are approved, first, by the WP leader and then by the Executive Board. The Coordinator is in charge of uploading the deliverables in the Participant Portal (the EU online system). The due date is the month in which the deliverables will be available, intending that the deadline for submission is the last day of the month indicated.

Project milestones can be found in Annex I, part A of the CLEANKER Grant Agreement (Table 1.3.4) and are major events. The Coordinator will be responsible of reporting the milestone in the Participant Portal (EU online system).

3.1.3 Detailed Gantt diagram

A Gantt diagram with resolution on task level is included below (Figure 3-3). In addition to main deliverables and project milestones, the diagrams also shows WP reporting periods. A Gantt diagram for each WP from 2 to 8 included in Annex 1, part B of the CLEANKER Grant Agreement is shown in Figure 3-4.

An inconsistency was detected in the plan in Annex 1, part A/B: the two CLEANKER workshops (MS12 and MS18) are scheduled for M24 and M26. The second workshop has to be handled in M36. Change implemented is shown in the detailed Gantt diagram below.

Figure 3-4: Gantt chart per WP with interconnections and dependency

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4. REPORTING PERIODS

4.1 Obligations

Monitoring the project implementation is a continuous task. From the list of the deliverables to be submitted to the Commission (see Table 3-2), there are three specific deliverables aimed at monitoring and reporting the progress of the work and the implementation of the project:

- **D1.3:** CLEANKER first reporting period (M18);
- **D1.4:** CLEANKER second reporting period (M36);
- **D1.5:** CLEANKER final report (M48).

There are contractual tasks that make the project monitoring most relevant at certain periods in project's life, in particular after each reporting period at the time of payments. CLEANKER has three reporting periods where project progress is reported and costs are declared to the INEA, which is operating under the power delegated by the European Commission.

Month 1 (M1) of CLEANKER is October 2017. The three reporting periods established in Article 20 of Annex 1, part A of the CLEANKER Grant Agreement are:

- **Period 1 for reporting (RP1) is M1-M18, i.e. October 2017-March 2019** (18 months). All reports must be submitted after two months, i.e. by May 31 2019.
- **Period 2 for reporting (RP2) is M19-M30, i.e. April 2019-March 2020** (11 months). All reports must be submitted after two months, i.e. by May 31 2020.
- **Period 3 for reporting (RP3) is M31-M48, i.e. April 2020-September 2021** (17 Months). All reports must be submitted after two months, i.e. by November 30 2021.

4.2 Periodic reports

4.2.1 Content

The content of the periodic reports has to be developed in accordance with Article 20.3 of the Grant Agreement. A template of the Periodic report is available in the folder "General Information" of the Partner Area of the CLEANKER website (www.cleanker.eu).

Technical report

The technical report has to describe the work carried out, the progress toward objectives (including deviations and dissemination activities) and the summary of publications during the specific reporting period.

According to Article 20.3 of the GA, its structure has to include the following sections:

- i. An explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries;
- ii. An overview of the progress towards the objectives of the action, including milestones, and deliverables identified in Annex 1;
- iii. A summary for publication by the Agency;

- iv. Answers to questionnaire covering issues related to the action implementation and the economic and societal impact.

The technical report will be built, during the reporting period, continuously (Part A - by a continuous update through the participant portal) and periodically (Part B – by submitting a PDF). In particular:

- Part A:
 - o Publishable summary
 - o Deliverables, milestones, risks, etc.
 - o Answers to the questionnaire.
- Part B:
 - o Explanation of the work carried out by the beneficiaries and overview of progress;
 - o Update of the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results;
 - o Explanations on deviations from DoA.

Financial report

The periodic financial report contains:

- A **Cost statement** (Annex 4 to the GA) containing the explanations on the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties;
- A periodic summary of the **Financial Statements** (including the request for payments) auto-generated by the electronic system and electronically signed by the Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN).

4.2.2 Data collection and roles

Beneficiaries have to provide inputs for the preparation of the periodic and the final reports. The Coordinator will launch the process of collecting technical inputs at the end of M18 (31/03/2019) and M30 (31/03/2020). The WP leaders will prepare the technical inputs requested, the Coordinator will set the Technical report that will be reviewed and approved by the EB members.

The process of collecting financial information will be launched one month later, namely, M19 (30/04/2019) and M31 (30/04/2010). All beneficiaries shall complete electronically the model for the Financial Statement via the Participant Portal. The Individual Financial Statements of each beneficiary shall be signed electronically by the corresponding Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) appointed by each organization.

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4.2.3 Timing and submission

Within 60 days following the end of each reporting period, two reports have to be submitted (Article 20 of the GA), the technical report and the financial report. In addition to the periodic report, for the last reporting period, a final report has to be prepared. The submission of the periodic reports to the European Commission is responsibility of the Coordinator that will use electronic exchange system according to Article 52 of the GA.

At the end of each reporting period, the Commission has to evaluate and approve project reports and distribute the corresponding payments within 90 days from receiving the periodic report (see Article 21.3 of the Grant Agreement).

4.3 Final report – Content, timing and submission

At the end of the project, a Final Report has to be submitted. Its content is compulsory and determined by the Commission according to Article 20.4 of the Grant Agreement. The final report must include the following:

- a) a ‘final technical report’ with a summary for publication containing:
 - v. an overview of the results and their exploitation and dissemination;
 - vi. the conclusions on the action, and
 - vii. the socio-economic impact of the action;
- b) a ‘final financial report’ containing:
 - viii. a ‘final summary financial statement’, created automatically by the electronic exchange system, consolidating the individual financial statements for all reporting periods and including the request for payment of the balance and
 - ix. a ‘certificate on the financial statements’ (CFS) (drawn up in accordance with GA Annex 5) for each beneficiary and for each linked third party, if it requests a total contribution of EUR 325.000 or more, as reimbursement of actual costs and unit costs calculated on the basis of its usual cost accounting practices (see GA Article 5.2 and Article 6.2, Point A).

The model of a CFS is compulsory and it should be drawn up in accordance with Annex 5. Please ask your auditors to follow strictly the model requested by the Commission.

According to the budget in DoA, the following partners are expected to provide a CFS within CLEANKER: LEAP, BUZZI, CSIC, IKN, LUT, TUT, USTUTT and VDZ.

The report completion and the review must occur in the 60 days after the end of the project. The costs incurred after the end of the project related to the final review meeting and completion of the report are eligible as long as the report is not submitted until the review meeting has taken place.

The Final report will be submitted by the Coordinator via the Participant Portal and the balance will be payed within 90 days.

4.4 Reporting Costs

At the end of each reporting period (M18, M30 and M48), each beneficiary will submit to the Project Coordinator the Cost Statement, the financial Statement and, at the end of RP3, the certificate on the financial statement as described in 4.2 and 4.3.

The deadlines for the submission of the documents are summarize in the following table:

Table 4-1: Deadlines for the submission of inputs to the Coordinator

RP	End of reporting period	Submission of Cost Statement to Coordinator	Electronic signature of Financial Statement (Form C) by the PFSIGN	Certificate on the financial statements (if equal to EUR 325.000 or more)	Submission to EC (By Coordinator)
1	31/03/2019	1/05/2019 - 15/05/2019	16/05/2019 – 23/05/2019		1/06/2019
2	31/03/2020	1/05/2020 - 15/05/2020	16/05/2020 – 23/05/2020		1/06/2020
3	30/09/2021	7/10/2021 – 15/10/2021	16/10/2021 – 20/10/2021	16/10/2021 – 20/10/2021	1/11/2021

The costs declared have to be eligible according to Article 6 of the GA. Explanation and example can be found in the latest version of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement (available in the Participant Portal Documents).

Levels of detail expected follow:

- **Personnel costs** (amounts, name, function, statute (additional or permanent), monthly rate or hourly rate (A) and working time spent on which WP (in month if monthly rate given in A or in hours if hourly rate is given in A),
- **Travel costs** (amount by travel and by participants, name of travellers, exact dates (dd/mm/yyyy), origin/destination (from/to), and detailed purpose of the travel),
- **Depreciation costs** of equipment (amount claimed, nature of the equipment, price by equipment (excl VAT), depreciation system (in years or month), % of use in the project)
- **Consumables** (amount by class of consumables, nature, list (when applicable), precise purpose and use of these consumables),
- **Subcontracting** (amount by subcontract, agreement EC (either technical annex or specific agreement (if so please provide a copy of the agreement), nature of the tasks, name of subcontractor and link of these with the project),
- **Other costs** (class covering costs not covered by previous H2020 class – amounts by cost, very precise details about the nature of each cost),
- **Indirect costs** (25% flat rate). Indirect costs are calculated on the basis of the flat rate of 25% of the eligible direct costs (Article 5.2 of the Grant Agreement) from which subcontracting and in-kind contributions are excluded.

4.4.1 Keeping records

The submission of a Certificate on the Financial Statements (CFS), Annex 5 of the GA, does NOT waive the right of the Commission to carry out its own audit which may be launched

at any time and up to five years after the end of the project (see Article 17 and Article 22 of the GA). Therefore, all beneficiaries are have to keep CLEANKER supporting documentation up to five years after payment of the balance.

This list summarises all supporting documents (per cost category) that may be requested by an auditor (see “Procedures” in Annex 5 for details):

Table 4-2: Supporting documents

Category	Supporting documents
Personnel Costs	<p>List of the persons included in the sample indicating the period(s) during which they worked for the action, their position (classification or category) and type of contract;</p> <p>Payslips of the employees;</p> <p>Time Sheets;</p> <p>Reconciliation of the personnel costs declared in the Financial Statement(s) with the accounting system (project accounting and general ledger) and payroll system;</p> <p>Information concerning the employment status and employment conditions of personnel included in the sample, in particular their employment contracts or equivalent;</p> <p>The Beneficiary's usual policy regarding payroll matters (e.g. salary policy, overtime policy, variable pay);</p> <p>Applicable national law on taxes, labour and social security.</p>
Subcontracting	<p>Annex 1;</p> <p>Financial Statement;</p> <p>Supporting documents on the selection and award procedure (invoices, proof of payment...);</p> <p>Supporting documents on the ensuring of best value for money.</p>
Other actual direct costs	
Travel	<p>Documents showing that travel and subsistence costs were consistent with the Beneficiary's usual policy for travel (tickets, including boarding passes, hotel bills...);</p> <p>Documents showing that travel costs are correctly identified and allocated to the action (report, records, minutes etc. indicating purpose and participants of the meetings):</p> <p>Mission approval forms.</p>

Other goods and services	Annex 1; Documents proving the allocation to the proper action and the entrance in the accounting system (invoices, proof of payment...); Supporting documents on the ensuring of best value for money; Supporting documents for depreciation (in line with the applicable rules in the Beneficiary's country and with the Beneficiary's usual accounting policy, e.g. depreciation calculated on the acquisition value) In case of rented equipment: Rental contract, inventory list of the rented equipment; proof of the investment values of the rented equipment
Bank statements (for coordinator)	Relating to the payments of the EC contributions and the distribution among partners.
Certificate on Financial Statement (CFS)	Copies of any auditor certification statements issued with a claim for cost reimbursement.

5. PROCEDURES

5.1 Decision making

Good working relationship among the project team members will be perused for quick resolution of problems and issues. Partners shall always try to reach an agreement. If not possible, conflicts have to be solved at the lowest level possible.

As a general principle, decisions are made at all levels and in all areas of the project's activities and a consensus should be achieved for decisions that affect more than one partner. The first level where to handle such a consensus is at the WP-level. If it cannot be found at this level, the Project Coordinator will mediate. If the PC cannot find a solution satisfying all partners, the issue will be escalated to the level of the General Assembly for a final decision, eventually though a vote (see Clauses 6.2.3 and 7.3.2 of the Consortium Agreement).

5.2 Working

Working procedures for meeting can be found in Section 6.2.2 of the Consortium Agreement. Here below a summary follows:

5.2.1 Notice of a meeting

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall give notice in writing of a meeting to each Member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Executive Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

5.2.2 Sending the Agenda

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each Member of that Consortium Body a written (original) agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	21 calendar days	10 calendar days
Executive Board	7 calendar days	7 calendar days

5.2.3 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the Members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any Member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other Members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Assembly	14 calendar days	7 calendar days
Executive Board	2 calendar days	2 calendar days

5.2.4 Decisions in meetings

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted according to voting procedures. Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the Coordinator circulates to all Members of the Consortium Body a written document, which is then agreed by the defined majority of all Members of the Consortium Body. Such document shall include the deadline for responses.

The decisions will be binding after the chairperson sends to all Members of the Consortium Body and to the Coordinator a written notification of this acceptance.

5.3 Documents

This section describes the processes to be used for document management and for related exchanges between project partners with the aim of assuring confidentiality, security, traceability, and consistency of information exchanged.

5.3.1 Deliverables

Deliverables must be submitted within the deadlines defined in Annex I to the Grant Agreement following these steps:

1. Download from «General Information» of the Partner Area the most recent version of the deliverable template
2. Once approved by all the authors and the WP leader, send the finished report in word format to the Coordinator with the WP leader in cc
3. The Coordinator:
 - a. will convert it in .pdf and Upload in Partner Area > Deliverables and milestones > Deliverables > WPX > Approved
 - b. will write an email to the EB members
4. If no objections within one week, the Coordinator will submit the deliverable to EU and copy the final version in Partner Area > Deliverables and milestones > Deliverables > WPX > Submitted

5.3.2 Milestones

Step to be followed for milestones' submission are:

1. Download from «General Information» of the Partner Area the most recent version of the milestone template
2. Upload the finished report in word format (Partner Area > Deliverables and milestones > Milestones > WPX > Public)
3. Write an email:
 - a. To the Coordinator confirming that all authors approve that their names are made public
 - b. To the WP leader informing that the milestone is ready for approval
4. When the WP leader will approve the milestone contents:
 - a. He will convert it in .pdf and move to Partner Area > Deliverables and milestones > Deliverables > WPX > Approved
 - b. He will write an email to the GA and EB members (coordinator in Cc)

5.3.3 Dissemination of results

All planned papers and other results to be disseminated are to be sent for CLEANKER partners approval to the Coordinator, to the WP leader, to the IMB members and all involved partners on Cc including information about:

- x. Where it is intended to be published/presented
- xi. A couple of sentences for orientation about the contents

Prior notice of any planned publication should be sent to the parties for approval at the latest 20 days before the intended submission date. Justified objections (in writing) are accepted within 10 calendar days (CA, 8.4.2.2).

In the CA there is no distinction among papers/abstracts/presentations, which all require the communication of the dissemination action “at least 20 calendar days before the publication”.

It was agreed, without any amendment to the CA, that this should be intended as follows:

- Papers and abstracts have to be distributed to the consortium (i.e. to the EB members) 20 calendar days before the submission;
- Presentations do not need to be distributed before they are presented, if the presented results are already contained in previously approved abstract and papers.

Steps to be followed:

1. The submitting partner updates the publication list (Partner Area > Results dissemination > «764816 CLEANKER List of Publications_Dissemination»)
2. The submitting partner uploads the publication in the appropriate folder (Partner Area > Results Dissemination > XXXproper folderXXX > For approval) and informs the Coordinator via email
3. The Coordinator notifies all the contacts involved about the publication requiring approval
4. The Coordinator notifies the EB and the IMB members and the lead author about the publication approval and will move the approved publication to folder «Approved» (in the same path of step 2).
5. When the published version of the paper/presentation/poster is available, the lead author informs the Coordinator via email and updates the publication list, including a link to the publication, if available.

5.4 Dissemination of results

Dissemination activities and publications will be governed by the Grant Agreement (Article 29.2) and the Consortium Agreement (see Section 8.4). Any dissemination of results (in any form, including electronic) must:

- display the EU logo (when displayed together with another logo, the EU logo will have appropriate prominence) and
- include the following text:

“This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Framework Programme under Grant Agreement n. 764816.

This work is supported by the China Government (National Natural Science Foundation of China) under contract No.91434124 and No.51376105”.

Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. A suggested disclaimer is:

“The European Commission support for the production of this publication does not constitute endorsement of the contents which reflects the views only of the authors,

and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein”.

5.4.1 Open Access

According to Article 29 of the Grant Agreement each beneficiary must ensure Open Access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results. Open Access provide ‘on-line and free of charge to the end-user’ access to scientific information.

Two different open access models can be distinguish:

- Green open access:
 - The published article or the final peer-reviewed manuscript is archived by the researcher – or a representative - in an online repository before, after or alongside its publication;
 - Access to the article is often – but not necessarily - delayed (‘embargo period’) as some scientific publishers may wish to recoup their investment by selling subscriptions and charging pay-per-download view fees during an exclusivity period.
- Gold open access:
 - An article is immediately provided in open access mode by the scientific publisher;
 - The associated costs are shifted away from readers, and instead charged to (for example) the university or research institute to which the researcher is affiliated, or to the funding agency supporting the research.

5.5 Reporting costs

The procedure to carry out the reporting for the costs (see 4.4) are:

1. Download the updated version of the template for the Cost Statement available in the CLEANKER Partner Area of CLEANKER website;
2. Fill it in detailing the costs at WP level. Make sure of the consistency between these costs and the costs set out in Annex II of the GA. Costs not foreseen in this section must be reported and duly explained in order to be accepted by the Commission;
3. Provide the Coordinator with the Cost Statement;
4. The Coordinator review the document;
5. Once approved by the Coordinator, costs shall be completed in SyGMA, creating Individual Financial Statements per beneficiary. The tool will create automatically the Financial Statements in accordance with Annex 4 of the Grant Agreement (see Figure 5-1). The persons of each organization allowed to complete the Financial Statement are Participant Contacts (PaCo) and Coordinator Contact (CoCo);
6. The Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) appointed by each organization can electronically sign the Individual Financial Statements.

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MODEL ANNEX 4 FOR H2020 GENERAL MGA — MULTI

FINANCIAL STATEMENT FOR [BENEFICIARY [name]/LINKED THIRD PARTY [name]] FOR REPORTING PERIOD [reporting period]

Eligible ¹ costs (per budget category)												Receipts		EU contribution				Additional information for indirect costs: Costs of in-kind contributions not used on premises. o
A. Direct personnel costs												Receipts	Reimbursement rate %	Maximum EU contribution ³	Requested EU contribution			
B. Direct costs of subcontracting		[C. Direct costs of fin. support]		D. Other direct costs		E. Indirect costs ²		[F. Costs of –]		Total costs								
A.1 Employees (or equivalent)		A.4 SME owners without salary		[C.1 financial support]		[D.1 Travel of large research infrastructure]		[F.1 Costs of –]		[F.2 Costs of –]		Receipts of the action, to be reported in the last reporting period, according to Article 6.2.E						
A.2 Natural persons under direct contract		A.5 Beneficiaries that are natural persons without salary		[C.2 Prizes]		[D.2 Equipment]		[F.3 Costs of –]		[F.4 Costs of –]								
A.3 Seconded persons												Receipts of the action, to be reported in the last reporting period, according to Article 6.2.E						
[A.6 Personnel for providing access]																		
Form of costs ⁴		Unit		Actual		Actual		Flat rate ⁵		[Unit][Lump sum]		Receipts of the action, to be reported in the last reporting period, according to Article 6.2.E						
a		Total b		Total c		d		[e]		f			g					
[short name beneficiary linked third party]								[h]		[i]		[j]						

The beneficiary/linked third party hereby confirms that:
The information provided is complete, reliable and true.
The costs declared are eligible (see Article 6).
The costs can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documentation that will be produced upon request or in the context of checks, reviews, audits and investigations (see Articles 17, 18 and 22).
For the last reporting period: that all the receipts have been declared (see Article 5.3.3).

¹ Please declare all eligible costs, even if they exceed the amounts indicated in the estimated budget (see Annex 2). Only amounts that were declared in your individual financial statements can be taken into account later on, in order to replace other costs that are found to be ineligible.

² See Article 6 for the eligibility conditions.

³ The indirect costs claimed must be free of any amounts covered by an operating grant (received under any EU or Euratom funding programme; see Article 6.2.E). If you have received an operating grant during this reporting period, you cannot claim any indirect costs.

⁴ This is the theoretical amount of EU contribution that the system calculates automatically (by multiplying the reimbursement rate by the total costs declared). The amount you request (in the column 'requested EU contribution') may be less.

⁵ See Article 5 for the form of costs.

⁶ Flat rate: 25% of eligible direct costs, from which are excluded: direct costs of subcontracting, costs of in-kind contributions not used on premises, direct costs of financial support, and unit costs declared under budget category F if they include indirect costs (see Article 6.2.E).

⁷ Only specific unit costs that do not include indirect costs.

Figure 5-1: Model Annex 4 - Financial Statement

5.6 Electronic signatures

1. PFSIGNS and PLSIGNS shall log in the Participant Portal with their ECAS account;
2. Go to “My project” tab and click “MP” (Manage Project) button of CLEANKER;
3. The PFSIGN or PLSIGN have the option “Sign and Submit”. Check consistency and if everything is correct click “Sign and Submit”;
4. The tool will ask you to enter again the ECAS password;
5. Click on “sign” and the process will be completed.

6. DOCUMENT HANDLING

All relevant documentation of CLEANKER will be allocated and available in the Partner Area on the CLEANKER website. The Partner Area will be updated according to the needs of the project, creating new folders or sub-folders in accordance to the needs. The idea is having a full repository of working documents, final documents, legal docs, templates and any ready-to-use doc generated by the project team members.

The Partner Area is structured as follows:

- **Contract:** here GA, CA and any other contract developed within CLEANKER will be found.
- **Budget/Finance.** An internal tool to monitor the CLEANKER effort in terms of costs and person-month will be found.

- *General Information.* Here templates available for all the documentation generated within CLEANKER will be found. Project templates are:
 - Power point presentation template
 - Minutes of meeting template
 - Deliverable template
 - H2020 Periodic report template
 - Certificate on financial statement template
 - Time-sheet for tracking time template
- *Meetings.* All the documentation related to Project Meeting (Minutes, pictures etc)
- *Deliverables and milestones.* Here deliverables and milestones divided per WP and per “For approval” and “approved” will be found.
- *Results dissemination.* A list of publication for approval and approved can be found.
- *EC reporting.* Documentation related to the three reporting periods.

7. PROJECT CHANGES – AMENDMENTS

The basic principle of the project is to carry out the tasks and activities within the time scheduled and resources foreseen as described in the Annex I (DoA) to the Grant Agreement.

Any changes in the status of a beneficiary shall be communicated to the Coordinator as soon as possible. The coordinator shall resolve queries and advise the beneficiaries. If required, the Project Coordinator will contact the EC Project Officer responsible and request clarifications and procedures to be followed.

Significant project changes and deviations from the work planned must be dealt with in writing. The participant involved or WP Leader proposing the change should forward a written communication to the General Assembly explaining the reason behind the proposed changes and direct consequences in terms of budget, work programme, etc.

As a general rule, an amendment to the Grant Agreement (GA) is necessary whenever the GA or its annexes shall be modified. In some cases, the GA gives the parties the possibility to carry out certain modifications without an amendment to the GA.

If an amendment to the GA is necessary, the Project Coordinator will request the amendment process to the Project Officer on behalf of the Consortium.

Small changes during the implementation of the activities and/or the plan defined in the DoA shall be understood as normal in a research project. However, these minor deviations shall be identified and explained in the DoA of the corresponding periodic report and corrective measures that were implemented (if any).

7.1 Changes which require an amendment

According to Article 55 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement, a sample list of cases where an amendment is necessary is:

- Removal of a beneficiary whose participation was terminated due to non-accession to the GA;
- Removal of a beneficiary whose participation was terminated for other reasons;
- Adding a new beneficiary;
- Change of beneficiary due to partial takeover;
- Removing a linked third party;
- Adding a linked third party;
- Change concerning a beneficiary/linked third party ‘not receiving EU funding’;
- Change of coordinator
 - The coordinator remains in the consortium
 - The participation of the coordinator is terminated
- Change of bank account for payments;
- Change of action’s title and/or acronym;
- Change of the starting date, action duration or reporting periods;
- Change to Annex I (Description of the Action);
- Change to Annex 2 and Annex 2a (estimated budget) or specific unit costs;
- Amendment reinstating the continuation of the GA
 - Request from the coordinator for suspension
 - Suspension by the Commission
 - Amendment reinstating the continuation of the GA

7.2 Changes which do not require an amendment

There are changes which do not require an amendment but shall be duly notified to the Commission via an information letter. According to Article 55 of the Annotated Model Grant Agreement, a sample list of cases where NO amendment is needed is:

- Budget transfer between beneficiaries or between budget categories (provided that the action is implemented in line with Annex 1);
- Change of name, address or other legal entity data (of beneficiaries/linked third parties);
- Change of beneficiary due to universal takeover.

NOMENCLATURE

AB	Advisory Board
AccAd	Account Administrator
AdT	Associazione Amici della Terra
BUZZI	Buzzi Unicem S.p.A.
CA	Consortium Agreement
CaL	Calcium Looping
CFS	Certificate on the Financial Statements
CoCo	Coordinator Contacts
CSIC	Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas
DoA	Description of the Action
EB	Executive Board
FSIGN	Financial Statement Authorised Signatory
GA	General Assembly
GA	Grant Agreement
IKN	IKN GmbH
IMB	Innovation Management Board
ITC-HCG	Italcementi – Heidelberg Cement Group
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LEAP	Laboratorio Energia Ambiente Piacenza
LEAR	Legal Entity Appointed Representative
LSIGN	Legal Statement Authorised Signatory
LUT	Lappeenranta University of Technology
PAB	Public Awareness Board
PaCo	Participant Contacts
PC	Project Coordinator
PCoCo	Primary Coordinator Contact
PFSIGN	Project Financial Statement Authorised Signatory
PLSIGN	Project Legal Statement Authorised Signatory
POLIMI	Politecnico di Milano
QUANTIS	Quantis Sàrl
RP	Reporting Period
TaMa	Task Managers
TaMe	Team Members
TSIU	Tsinghua University
TUT	Tallin University of Technology
USTUTT	University of Stuttgart
VDZ	Verein Deutscher Zementwerke gGmbH
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure

WP(s)

Work Package(s)